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Forensic accounting and financial crimes in Nigeria: Evidence from Local Government Administration in Nigeria

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Abstract

Forensic accounting is seen as a means for which financial crimes can be curbed. The study investigated the effect of forensic accounting on financial crimes. The survey design research was selected. The target population of the study was made up of professional accountants and auditors drawn from the 25 Local Government Areas of Delta State, Nigeria. The research has a sample size of forty and the method used in deriving it is personal judgment (a non-probability method). A well-structured five Likert scaled questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The collected data were then analyzed using the descriptive and the Pearson Correlation models. The finding of the study indicated that forensic audit has positive significant effect on money laundry reduction with a probability value of 0.000 and also a positive significant effect on bribery reduction with a probability value of 0.000. The study also found that litigation support has positive significant effect on money laundry reduction with a probability value of 0.042 and also a positive significant effect on bribery reduction with a probability value of 0.049. This led to the conclusion that forensic accounting has the capacity to reduce financial crime since there is a significant relationship. The work therefore recommends that forensic audit should be considered as a regular exercise whenever there is suspicion of money laundry; forensic audit department should be created in all anti-craft organizations to ensure proper investigation of financial crimes; forensic accounting experts should be involved in legal dispute and be allowed to provide evidence in the courtroom; and forensic accountant should be contacted for litigation services when there is a suspicious contract, to find out if bribe was given or taken.

Keywords: Forensic Accounting; Financial Crimes; Money Laundry; Forensic Auditing; Litigation Support.

1. Introduction

The widespread crimes in modern organizations have made traditional auditing and investigation inefficient and ineffective in the detection and prevention of the various types of economic and financial crimes confronting both private and public sectors, globally. Crime is a universal problem as no nations is resistant, although developing countries and their various states, local government and private sector suffer the most pain. The increasing sophistication of financial fraud requires that forensic accounting be added to the tools necessary to bring about the successful investigation and prosecution of those individuals involved in criminal activities. Financial crimes and fraudulent activities have been one of the most popular challenges to the global economy. It has been a subject of continuous debate in society as the cause of retardation in developing economies like Africa, Latin America, and Asia as seen today (Dada & Jimoh, 2020). Financial crimes and scams in modern organizations are perennial and have affected diverse organizations, irrespective of their sizes, natures and types. Gupta and Vij (2021) documented that financial crimes include manipulation of records or accounts, theft and embezzlement, diversion of funds, bribery and corruption. Thus, an increase in these frauds made the traditional accounting and auditing systems inefficient and ineffective in the detection and prevention of fraud in any society.

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Financial crime is seen as the act or the course of dishonesty, which is intentionally practiced by an individual in an organization in order to enhance illegal or unfair benefits to themselves (Ali et al., 2020). In this regard, financial crime can be classified as an act perpetrated in an organization such as fictitious accounts, unauthorized lending, unofficial borrowing, manipulating of vouchers, over-invoicing and fake payment. Dada and Jimoh (2020) reported that financial crimes include oil bunkering, embezzlement, bribery, looting, and money laundering, fraud, tax evasion and foreign exchange malpractice.

Financial crimes have been manifested globally, such as the scandal of Enron, WorldCom, and Cadbury (Chepngeno & Fred, 2020). However, the case of Nigeria where financial crimes are consistently reported and duly investigated by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) yet these criminal activities have continued to increase, raise concern about the situation in the Nigeria's ecosystem and, therefore, beg for a cursory look at other indices of arrest (Bello, 2020). Therefore, the increasing activities of financial crimes requires prompt engagement of forensic accounting in order to carry out any successful and discreet investigation, as well as the presentation of a probative evidential facts of the individuals associated with the criminal activities before the law court.

Forensic accounting is the use of laws of nature to the laws of man. This is normally carried out by forensic scientists as interpreters and examiners of facts and evidence in the legal case that also gives expert opinions concerning their findings in a court of law. Al Samara, Al-Afeef and Al Ali (2017) defined forensic accounting as the use of criminal methods and incorporation of investigative accounting issues and law processes to investigate and detect financial crimes and other economic malpractices.

Forensic accounting is targeted toward detecting and preventing an individual or corporate institution from conducting an act of questionable character or integrity. More so, forensic accounting is important in reducing fraud, fraudulent activities and corruption capable of destroying the national image and economic growth (Abdulrahman, 2019). In Nigeria, fraudulent practices have become much endemic and systemic, particularly in the public sector. However, Nigeria's case is unique, because both the magnitude and the frequency of occurrence of the menace continue to be on the increase. Forensic accounting is the tripartite practice of utilizing accounting, auditing and investigative skills to assist in legal matters. It is a specialized field of accounting that describes engagements resulting from actual or anticipated disputes or litigation (Okoye et al., 2019). It can, therefore, be seen as an aspect of accounting that is suitable for legal review and offers the highest level of assurance. Ehioghien and Atu (2016) opined that forensic accounting encompasses three major areas, investigation, dispute resolution and litigation support.

Forensic accounting has been identified as a tool for detecting and implementing of white-collar Investigations. However, the alarming increase in the cases of financial crimes and other fraudulent activities in Nigeria require the visibility of forensic accounting services. This is the motivation upon which this research was carried out.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Key institutions like Independence Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC), Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) were established to fight financial crimes corruption. All these could not work effectively because of various challenges like politicization and blackmail, constitutional immunity as stated in section 308 of Nigerian constitution, public apathy and doubtful attitudes towards anti-corruption work, and slow justice. Financial crimes have been manifested globally, such as the scandal of Enron, WorldCom, and Cadbury (Chepngeno & Fred, 2020). However, the case of Nigeria where financial crimes are consistently reported and duly investigated by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) yet these criminal activities have continued to increase, raise concern about the situation of financial crimes in the Nigeria's ecosystem and, therefore, beg for a cursory look at other indices of arrest (Bello, 2020). Therefore, the increasing activities of financial crimes requires prompt engagement of forensic accounting in order to carry out any successful and discreet investigation, as well as the presentation of a probative evidential facts of the individuals associated with the criminal activities before the law court. When forensic accounting is increased, it is expected that financial crimes will reduce due to the fact that forensic accounting involves looking for the thief.

Forensic audit was undertaken on the Niger Delta Development Commission yet not much was heard about it as the report seemed to be shrouded in secrecy. This has also questioned the credibility of fighting financial crimes by means of forensic accounting. This study therefore is carried out to solve the puzzle and give an answer on the possibility of reducing financial crimes in Nigeria through proper application of forensic accounting.

1.2. Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were stated:

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Forensic audit and the reduction of money laundry in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Forensic audit and the reduction of bribery in Nigeria.
- H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Litigation Support and the reduction of Money Laundry in Nigeria.
- H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between Litigation Support and the reduction of Bribery in Nigeria.

2. Conceptual Review

2.1. Forensic Accounting

Forensic accounting has evolved as a means of checking fraud since the traditional accounting system and auditing have failed in various areas in the conduct of curbing these governmental and private leakages and fraudulent injections. Forensic accounting is seen as taking a more advanced role in fraud prevention, detection, and management. Forensic accounting is the integration of accounting, auditing, and investigative skills.

Forensic means searching, examining, tracking and gathering factual information applicable to the court. According to Orsaa and Ezekiel (2017), forensic accounting is the application of accounting concepts and techniques to legal problems. Forensic accounting is the specialty practice area of accounting that describes engagements that result from actual or anticipated disputes or litigation. In addition, Ezejiolor, et al, (2019) define forensic accounting as "the practice of utilizing accounting, auditing, and investigative skills to assist in legal matters, typically related to financial fraud or disputes".

It demands reporting, where accountability of the fraud is established and the report is considered as evidence in a court of law or administrative proceedings (Ogwiji, 2023). However, the application of forensic accounting role and effectiveness have raised serious concerns as it has been argued that it is used mainly aftermath of the fraud to find the perpetrators and carried out in order to avoid future occurrences. As a tool mainly for legal purposes, the sophistication of fraud perpetrators and the role of insiders who know how to bypass the system and not get caught have also questioned the effectiveness and need for forensic accounting. In addition, there has not been an adequate emphasis, especially on survey evidence on how forensic accounting can help curtail financial and economic crimes beyond the several unreliable views that abound.

The scope of forensic accounting includes the identification of financial irregularities, the quantification of losses resulting from fraud, and the presentation of financial evidence in legal proceedings. It has to do with the investigation of financial fraud, the tracing of assets, and the provision of expert witness testimony. Micah, et al, (2023) assert that the scope of forensic accounting includes the identification of fraudulent financial activities, the quantification of losses, and the provision of expert testimony in legal proceedings.

2.2. Forensic Audit

The forensic auditors, though not popular in Nigeria, are hired occasional with the sole aim of unearthing fraudulent activities (Edori & Edori, 2018). Forensic audit is a viable weapon for investigating financial frauds, embezzlement, corruption, money laundry and the likes. Forensic audit is all about using specific investigative and audit procedures and accounting principles to obtain evidence applicable to the court (Lawan, et al, 2018). Forensic audit is the application of auditing principles, investigative techniques and legal procedures to establish damages, loss or gain on properties, and collecting evidence which is suitable for court purpose (Mohammed & Peter, 2016).

Forensic auditing emerged due to the high incidence of fraud. It originated around the 1800s and was coined by Peloubet in 1946 (Manas, 2014). It is a specialized area of auditing practices employed to provide suitable evidence that is relevant to legal issues (Okoye, et al, 2019). Forensic audit is capable of prosecuting the fraudsters, embezzlers and other financial criminals or suspects. The techniques of forensic audit include business intelligence, forensic analytics, data base collection, whistle blowing and background investigation (Nenyiaba, et al, 2015). Data mining is the searching and analyzing of data in the gigabytes of systems to root out already buried useful information due to the passage of time. Ratio analysis may be computed to determine the wellbeing and to check on the financial health of a firm which

could also point to waste and abuse of funds and fraud. In ratio analysis results, if the highest value to the lowest value is close to 1, then no much accounts doctoring exists but if it large, it indicates the possibility of fraud (Onodi, et al, 2015).

2.3. Litigation Support

Litigation Support provides assistance of an accounting nature in a matter involving existing or pending litigation. It deals primarily with issues related to the quantification of economic damages. Oyedele et al.(2014) defined litigation support services as the use of accounting, auditing, and communication skills to aid legal procedures and in these circumstances, the forensic accountant could be retained to serve as an expert witness, master, or special master. In the same vein, the American Bar Association (2021) defines litigation support as "the provision of assistance to attorneys in any phase of a legal matter, including pretrial, trial, and post-trial activities. Litigation support is the process by which forensic accountants provide advice to attorneys on complex accounting matters that are relevant to a legal dispute (Micah, 2023).

The scope of litigation support includes the analysis of financial data, the preparation of financial reports and exhibits, and the provision of expert witness testimony. A typical litigation support assignment would be calculating the economic loss resulting from a breach of contract. Litigation support is one of the most common reasons to hire a forensic accountant. "Litigation Support", provides assistance of an accounting nature in a matter involving existing or pending litigation. It deals primarily with issues related to the quantification of economic damages. A typical litigation support assignment would be calculating the economic loss resulting from a breach of contract.

2.4. Financial Crimes

The manifestation of economic and financial crime can be comfortably described as wild and endemic. Economic crime is an illegal act in which beneficiary, perpetrators or offenders' major motivation appears to be economic gain. Edori (2018) describes it as a crime that does not involve violence which is equivalence to normal economy disruption resulting in financial loss or earning that is deliberately earned by a person or group of persons in organization in a way that is not permissive or acceptable to legislative enactment which govern the economic activities is violated. Financial crimes which may involve fraud are crime against property. It involves the unlawful conversion of the ownership of property belonging to another to one's own personal use and benefit. Financial crimes are the "violent, criminal and illicit activities committed with the objective of earning wealth illegally in a manner that violates existing legislation" (Ezejiolor, et al, 2016).

Accordingly, economic and financial crime is a crime involving the unlawful conversion of the ownership of property belonging to another to one's own personal use and benefit (Oseni, 2017), thus a crime against property. Economic and financial crimes comprise a broad array of activities ranging from fraud to actively manipulating stock market or proceeds from crime laundering. Economic and financial crime has resulted to institutional shock, bankruptcy, failure and fall of potential and great output thereby leading to economic comatose, disruption and deprivation, crises and saboteur (Umanhonlen, 2020). These include bribery, illicit monies, nepotism, cronyism, kickbacks, political donations, artificial pricing and frauds of all kinds. Embezzlement is a form of financial crimes involving improper stealing of money from someone whom one owes the duty of responsibilities. Corruption is stealing from the poor. Money laundering is the illicit flying of funds to another country. Bribery is when money or other valuable things are offered to influence a person or a situation. Extortion is demanding for money or other material things to do a favor.

Financial crimes include but are not limited to bribery and corruption, tax evasion, treasury looting, illegal oil bunkering, theft of intellectual property, illegal mining, financial child labour, prohibited goods, money laundering, counterfeiting currency, drug trafficking and other illicit activities of gaining illegal wealth (Joseph, et al, 2016). It may involve additional criminal acts such as burglary, computer crime, aiding, elder abuse, including violent such as theft, armed robbery or murder, hence, carried out by an individual, groups, organization, corporations, government, states or community. This includes a range of activities which are not legal such as money laundering and evasion of tax. Therefore, Umanhonlen, et al (2020) posit that the quantum of loss that have been involved in economic and financial crimes is huge, and cannot be qualified, it as grievous as tsunamis and/or economic recession, expert says if not checked can lead to partial close down of business as a result of collapse of current incremental economic gains in potential output. Fraud included wide varies of practices out of law to possess or change the existed financial conditions for the benefit of third party.

Financial Crime has become a reoccurring trend in Nigeria. FBI (2018) report shows that Nigeria is among the top 5 hubs of fraudsters as most perpetrators come from the country. Nigeria Deposit Insurance Commission audited account of (2019) and (2020) reported a high amount of N204.65 billion and N120.79 billion respectively, of monies lost by banks to fraud annually and the Central Bank of Nigeria (2022) reported that N2.73 trillion out of the N3.23 trillion

currency in circulation, was outside the vaults of commercial banks across the country, the various reports painfully attest to the high rate of fraud in Nigeria and this necessitated the CBN to collaborate with the Nigeria Intelligence Unit (NFIU) and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission on money laundry on an illicit financial transaction. In recent times, a number of fraudulent acts have been committed both in the public sector and private sector of the economy. These in no doubt are perpetrated under the supervision of the accountant and internal auditors of the organization.

This technique can be employed to effectively investigate and detect cases of corruption in Nigeria. Fraud and fraudulent cases in some countries increased the demand for forensic accounting (Umanhonlen, et al, 2020). In Nigeria, the present and past governments have made commitment, enacted several laws with the aim of combating economic and financial crime but none has made any significant improvement, neither has it impact felt among Nigerians (Edori, 2018). Abuh and Acho (2018) agreed that crime is a universal constraint as no nation is exempted, although, developing countries like Nigeria and several other states which suffers of the scourge as it oppose and negatively affected the nation economy. In Nigeria today, there is alarming and increasing number of frauds and fraudulent activities. This emphasizes and informed the visibility of forensic accounting services. Gbegi and Habila (2017) admit that nowadays series of economic and financial frauds and other fraudulent activities are evolving, as well being committed barely in all organizations including private and public sectors of global economy.

It follows therefore that if these are not effectively addressing the menace of economic and financial crime has potential of greatly negates the nation economic stability. Consequently, rate of it occurrence is highly disturbing and growing rapidly especially in Nigeria economy. Though, with the involvement of forensic accountant in fraud evaluation, management and prevention, fraud still hold to its beam and being committed on daily basis. Modern organized corporate fraud are sophisticated thereby the need to response to the charging criminal tendencies and threats with the skill of investigation, and to rigorously tackle the menace by forensic accountant and legal experts. However, the increasing sophistication of financial fraud requires that forensic accounting assume or be added to tools necessary to bring the successful investigation and prosecution of these individuals involved in criminal activities (Olola, 2016). Nevertheless, financial crimes aim of serving financial/economic advantages either directly or indirectly, thus, identifying the causes of fraud is very difficult because modern day's organizations frauds involve a complex web of conspiracy and deception that often mast the actual cause.

2.5. Money Laundry

Fraudsters use money laundering tactics to run their schemes without leaving a paper trail. Money laundering remains a major and costly form of fraud for both businesses and the overall global economy. Money laundering is the process by which large amount of illegally obtained money (from drug trafficking, terrorist activity or other serious crimes) is given the appearance of having originated from the Legitimate source. Money laundering is the processing of criminal proceeds to disguise their illegal origin. This process is of critical importance, as it enables the criminal to enjoy these profits without jeopardising their source.

Money laundering has been addressed in the UN Vienna 1988 Convention Article 3.1 describing Money Laundering as:

“the conversion or transfer of property, knowing that such property is derived from any offense(s), for the purpose of concealing or disguising the illicit origin of the property or of assisting any person who is involved in such offense(s) to evade the legal consequences of his actions.”

Money laundering is a process that typically follows three stages to finally release laundered funds into the legal financial system.

Stages of Money Laundering:

- Placement (i.e. moving the funds from direct association with the crime)
- Layering (i.e. disguising the trail to foil pursuit)
- Integration (i.e. making the money available to the criminal from what seem to be legitimate sources)

In reality, money laundering cases may not have all three stages, some stages could be combined, or several stages repeat several times. For instance, Cash from drug sales is divided into small amounts then they are deposited by “money mules” and afterward transferred as payment for services to a shell company. In this case, the placement and layering are done in one stage.

2.6. Bribery

Bribery is a complex phenomenon rooted in both individual motives and the greater institutional context. Experimental research into causal mechanisms that drive bribing behavior is still scarce. Bribery is still a wicked problem that does not seem to go away so easily, or at all, in many countries across the world. Bribery comes with very high social costs, undermining the sense of fairness. Bribery is a multi-faceted and many-faced phenomenon. We start from the Cambridge Dictionary's common sense definition as "an attempt to make someone do something for you by giving the person money, presents, or something else that they want."

According to Ramdani and van Witteloostuijn (2014), bribery is defined as the corrupt payment, receipt, or solicitation of a private favor for actions or decisions from influential or powerful agents or authorities which could be public officials, corporations or people inside corporations to generate private benefits of the briber.

Heidenheimer (2009) distinguishes three *shades* of bribery: Black bribery, gray bribery, and white bribery. Black bribery is a particular action that by majority consensus of public opinion should be condemned and punished on grounds of principle. Gray bribery implies that limited elements in society, usually elites, may want to see the actions punished and that the majority may well be ambiguous. White bribery is tolerated by the majority of both elite and mass opinion, and attempts to punish this form of bribery are not likely to find public support

3. Theoretical Review

3.1. White Collar Crimes Theory (WCCT)

This study is pinned in the WCCT. The theory is a general theory of financial crimes coined by Ross in 1907 but further developed by Sutherland in 1938. This theory established that the majority of financial crimes (FCs) are undetectable. However, Ross used a term called "Crimanoid" to mean a person who uses illegal opportunities for public stealing from the poor (Izedonmi & Ibadin, 2012). Sutherland referred to FCs as the carefully as well as intentionally perpetrated financial crimes (Egbunike & Amakor, 2013). Sutherland claimed that poverty is not a driving force for committing WCCs; it is rarely committed by the poor (Egbunike & Amakor, 2013). The WCCT discusses the issues relating to how various financial crimes are being perpetrated with the kings of FCs falling into this category. Thus, the theory fits into this research.

3.2. Empirical Review

Ogwiji (2023) examined the effect of attributes of forensic accountants– Investigation of financial Crime and Corruption Skill (ICC), Knowledge and Expertise (KE), Litigation Support Services (LSS) on the financial crime (FC) in Nigerian public sector. The study employed cross-sectional design and a survey method. Of the 110 questionnaires distributed, 53 questionnaires were returned valid and analysed. The study used PLS-SEM (SmartPLS 3.0) and IBM SPSS ver. 20.0 as the primary statistical analysis tools. The results of the study confirm that Knowledge and Expertise and Support Services of a forensic accountant has a significant positive effect on Financial Crime and it shows that investigation of crime and corruption has an insignificant negative effect on financial crime. Thus, the findings revealed that the forensic accountant attributes have significantly higher levels of KE, LSS on FC concerning fraud prevention, detection, management and response. Also, investigation of corruption discourages financial crime though not on high. The implication of this study might result in the overall reduction of fraud and fraudulent acts, promote institutional, regulatory and legal framework, and create awareness amongst the accounting and auditing institutions in the Nigerian public sector.

Oseni (2017) examined the effects of forensic accounting services on fraud and financial crime detection and prevention in Nigeria. The survey designed was used in the study with a sample size of 160 consisting of Auchi Polytechnic, Edo State Ministry of Finance, Audit Firms and Federal Inland Revenue Services. The simple random technique was used as the sampling technique, while the chi-square was employed in the data analysis. The tests of hypothesis were done using Microsoft Excel 2010 version. Tests were carried out at a significant level of 5% and three degree of freedom. The paper concludes that financial crimes and fraud have serious negative effect on human capital and infrastructural development in developing economies, especially countries like Nigeria. Forensic accounting services provide corporate organizations with the necessary tools to detect and prevent frauds and financial crimes.

Umanhonlen, et al (2020) appraised the role of forensic accountant in combating economic and financial crimes in Nigeria. The paper explored relevance components of economic and financial crimes and extensively discussed concepts

of crime and criminality, corruption, white collar and cybercrimes. Specifically, the study reviews the historical antidotes of forensic accounting, emphasizes on the role of forensic accounting science in litigation and forensic accountant ensuring economic and financial crime immersed. More so, the study identifies basis for future research, some potential crimes factors and forensic accounting science expert's opinion in crime scene as well as reviewed prior studies and gap envisaged. Essentially, the study reviewed theoretical issues using qualitative approach thereby involving a survey of literature to decipher relevant issues. It therefore sought that forensic accounting serves the basis for investigation, expert witness testimony and opinion of expert in lawsuit so as to unravel crimes, and reach resolution for recovering. However, concludes that there is need to involve and embrace accounting expert science in all facets of crime investigation in order to accelerate detections and ameliorate incidences of failed attempt on crime recovery related to economic and financial crimes.

Abuh and Acho (2020) examined the extent in which forensic accounting enhances the detection of economic and financial crimes as well as improving Nigeria economy stability. A Population of 164 with 116 responses was reviewed. The study employed Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for data analysis; Taro Yamane Statistical Technique with five point likert Scale of Descriptive Statistics to obtain the sample size and to collect data respectively. Both Primary and Secondary Data were used. Result showed a positive correlation, that is, forensic accounting enhances detection of economic and financial crimes as well as improves Nigeria economic stability.

Jacob (2021) examined the effect of forensic accounting on financial fraud management in Nigeria's public sector. The study employed primary data collected using a well- structured questionnaire administered to two hundred and fifty respondents from EFFC, ICPC, Office of the Accountant General, Office of the Auditor General and other practicing accountants in the country. The data gathered through the questionnaire were analysed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed that forensic accounting practices have a positive effect on fraud management. Also, the study found that forensic accounting has a significant influence on fraud detection and prevention and that forensic litigation has a significant positive effect on the recovery of funds lost to fraud.

Gupta and Vij (2021) examined the effect of forensic accounting on the detection and prevention of financial fraud in the Indian Corporate Sector. The study utilizes diverse techniques viz. Benford's Law, Theory of Relative Size Factor, and data mining in the detection and prevention of financial frauds. Responses from 100 accounting professionals were collected through snowball and judgment sampling. The study found that forensic accounting practices have a positive and significant effect on fraud detection and prevention in the Indian Corporate sector.

Bello (2020) examines the effect of forensic accounting technology on fraud detection in Nigeria. The study used a qualitative approach by administering questionnaires with both structured and semi-structured questions. A total of 38 Investigators from the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) were used as a sample for the study. The study revealed a significant relationship between forensic accounting technological tools and fraud detection in Nigeria. The study established that forensic accounting is solving fraud issues and using technology to aid fraud detection in Nigeria.

Chepngeno and Fred (2020) analyses the effects of litigation support services on fraud mitigation in firms listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). The study population comprised all firms listed at the NSE. The study employed a non-probability sampling (purposive sampling) technique to select the sample frame. Primary data were collected from purposively selected staff working with the aforesaid firms. The data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 and Statistics data (STATA) version 13 analytical tools. The results of the study revealed that litigation support services have significant correlations with fraud mitigation.

Eyo and Ebahi (2020) examine the effect of forensic accounting and litigation support services on fraud detection in Nigerian companies. The study data were sourced from the primary sources and with the help of structured questionnaires of two segments administered to the employees of Zenith Bank Nigeria Plc. and Union Bank Nigeria Plc. in Calabar, Cross River State. The data collected were presented with the help of tables and interpreted with the help of inferential statistics using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The study revealed that forensic accounting and litigation support do not have a significant effect on fraud detection in Nigerian companies.

Okoye and Mbanugo (2020) assess the effect of forensic Accounting on fraud cases in tertiary institutions in South East Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 470 account staff in 7 public tertiary institutions in South East Nigeria along with interviews conducted with those ministries out of which 350 were filled and returned. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used as a statistical tool to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that forensic accounting significantly reduces the occurrence of fraud

cases in the tertiary institutions in South East Nigeria and that there is a significant difference between Professional Forensic Accountants and Traditional External Auditors, and therefore, the use of Forensic Accountants can help better in detecting and preventing fraud cases in the tertiary institution's sector.

Ali et al., (2020) examine the impact of forensic accounting on fraud detection in the UAE banking sector: a study on Islamic and conventional banks. The study utilized cross-sectional survey research. The descriptive research design was employed for the study. The study used both qualitative and quantitative data. The study sampling technique for the research is purposive sampling. 200 employees have used as a sample size and a non-probability sampling technique was used in the study. A questionnaire was employed as an instrument used to gather data from a chosen sample and a five Likert scale was adopted in constructing the questionnaires. SPSS version 23 and SMART PLS were used to analyse the extracted data from the respondents. The findings of this research study show that there is a significant impact of forensic accounting on the detection of fraud within the Banking Industry in the UAE.

Dada and Jimoh (2020) investigated the effect of forensic accounting on financial crimes in the Nigerian public sector. Forensic accounting was proxy by litigation support service on the reduction of financial crime in the Nigerian public sector. The study adopted a survey research design and a linear regression technique was used to analyse the empirical data collected through questionnaires and oral interviews and the hypothesis formulated was also tested. The findings of the study revealed that litigation support services had a significant but negative effect (reduction) on financial crimes in the Nigerian public sector.

Abdulrahman (2019) examined the effect of forensic accounting on fraud prevention in the Nigerian public sector. The study focused on how forensic accounting prevents fraud in Nigeria's Public Sector and to determine whether forensic accounting prevents fraud in Nigeria's Public Sector. The study data were collected from secondary sources or Content Analysis. Based on the analysis of the study, it established that forensic accounting has a significant positive influence on fraud prevention.

Samuel (2019) investigated the effect of forensic accounting on the detection of fraud risk indicators in public enterprises in Ondo state, Nigeria. The population of the study was the entire staff of the public enterprises in Ondo State with a sample of 238 purposively targeted from two groups of respondents. The study sourced primary data through the use of a questionnaire, while secondary sources were textbooks, published materials like journals and internet facilities. The study made use of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS 2.1) software to analyse the collected data. The z-test research techniques were used to analyse and interpret the data collected. The results revealed that forensic accounting does have a significant effect with regard to the detection of fraud risk indicators in Public Enterprises. That is, effective use of forensic accounting could help in the detection of fraud risk indicators that often leads to the continuous perpetration of fraud in the Public Enterprises in Ondo State.

Akani and Ogbeide (2017) examined the effect of forensic accounting on fraudulent practices in the Nigerian public sector. The study employed the survey descriptive research design. The population consisted of all public institutions in Edo State, Nigeria. A sample of ten (10) government establishments, both Federal and State-owned were randomly selected. A structured four-scale Likert-type questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents who were mainly internal auditors, chief accountants, executive directors and directors of the selected institutions. Data were analysed using frequency counts and simple percentages methods. Findings from the study indicated that forensic accounting had a significant influence on the reduction of fraudulent practices in the Nigerian public sector.

Edheku and Akpoveta (2020) explored the impact of forensic accounting on fraud detection in public and private sectors in Abuja metropolis, Nigeria, from the accountants' perspective. The study adopted descriptive survey design. A sample of 43 accounting officers from selected four Federal Ministries of Government and five private Multinational Organizations operating in the Abuja metropolis, Nigeria was used. A validated questionnaire containing 10 items with an overall reliability of 0.73 established by Cronbach alpha was used for data collection. Mean and standard was used to answer the research question while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that accounting officers in the private and public sectors strongly agree that forensic accounting has an impact on fraud detection and did not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the impact of forensic accounting on fraud detection in the Abuja metropolis. The study concluded that genuine compliance of forensic accounting principles by internal and external auditors will not only reduce corporate frauds but will also improve the financial reporting quality of accountants in the public and private sectors of the business world. It was recommended among others that government should establish an independent forensic accounting agency with legal provisions that will enable them to detect, monitor and report fraudulent activities in the business environment in Nigeria.

Anuolam, et al (2017) examined the significance of forensic accounting and financial crisis in Nigeria. A Sample of 98 respondents was selected from a population of 140 using the Taro Yemen formula. 90 questionnaires were returned fully and correctly completed by the respondents. Regression analysis, correlation coefficient, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and E-view 7 Geometric software were used to analyze the data. The analysis shows that forensic accounting is significant in the face of the increasing fraudulent practices in Nigeria. The study recommended that the government should make forensic accounting compulsory for all accounting majors in the University and create enabling environment for the practice of forensic accounting in the country.

Adesina, et al (2020) studied how Forensic Audit Influence Fraud Control: Evidence in Nigeria's Deposit Money Banks (DMBs). The population consists of 22 DMBs in Nigeria. A sample of seventeen (17) banks was selected for the study. The survey research design was employed while the statistical tool used for the analysis of data was Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The result showed that forensic audit is a very important requirement for effectual and well-organized control of financial frauds in the Nigerian DMBs.

Uniamikogbo, et al (2019) studied “forensic audit and fraud detection and prevention in Nigerian banking sectors”. The population of the study consists of 16 DMBs listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study adopted the ex-post facto research method, thus secondary data was used. The data collected were analyzed using the statistical package for social science. The study reveals that DMBs have to increase how they apply forensic auditing in fighting fraud.

Bassey (2018) investigated “the effect of forensic accounting on the management of fraud in microfinance institutions in Cross River State”. The sample comprised 55 managers out of a population of 65. The survey method was used. Primary and secondary data were also used. The Ordinary Least Square procedure was used in testing hypotheses. The implication of the outcome shows that active engagement of forensic investigation and litigation support decreases fraud in the sampled companies. Managers of the sampled firms were encouraged to focus more on forensic accounting thereby monitoring and investigating alleged persons who commit frauds. Olaoye and Olanipekun (2018) carried out a study on the Impact of Forensic Accounting and Investigation on Corporate Governance in Ekiti State. A sample size of 92 respondents was selected out of a population of 120 forensic accountants and practitioners. The study adopted a survey and explanatory research design. The data collected were analyzed using Binary Logistics Regression Technique. The study revealed that forensic accounting and investigation have an impact on Corporate Governance.

Agbata, et al (2017) studied the “anatomy of pension fraud in Nigeria: its motives, the management and the future of the Nigerian pension scheme”. The population of the study consisted of 435 accountants, auditors, finance officers and pensioners of some selected institutions in Anambra state. The sample size was 417. Data were collected from primary source with the aid of a questionnaire. The statistical tool adopted in the analysis of the data was Multiple Regression Analysis using Minitab ver. 17. The research outcomes revealed that the pension scheme in existence in Nigeria seems not to be effective because of raging and disturbing pension frauds committed almost on daily basis. Also, fraud has constantly been a stumbling block in the effective management of Nigerian pension funds.

Dabor, et al (2017) studied “Forensic Accounting and Fraud Control in the Nigerian Banking sector”. The population is the workers of the entire Banks of Nigeria. The sample size was made up of 50 respondents. Likert scale questionnaire was used to obtain the data from the respondents. The z-test statistical tool was used to examine the difference in response. The findings indicate that the adoption of forensic accounting will lead to a reduction in financial statement fraud in Nigeria's Banking Sector.

Aigienohuwa, et al (2017) examined “the effectiveness of forensic accounting and fraud mitigation in the Nigerian banking industry”. Primary data was obtained by questionnaires. The result showed that forensic accounting significantly minimizes fraud in Nigerian banks and improves greatly on their internal control systems. Bank regulators and shareholders were encouraged to sternly impose forensic accounting of banks and insist that internal control and internal audit staff practice it.

Oseni (2017) examined “Forensic Accounting and Financial Fraud in Nigeria: problems and prospects”. A sample size consisting of 140 respondents was used. The survey research design was employed using a Likert scale questionnaire. The statistical tool used for the analysis of data was the chi-square. The finding revealed that Forensic Accounting Services provide corporate organization with the necessary tools to detect and prevent Fraud and Financial Crimes.

4. Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design with a population of fifty respondents made up of 25 Auditors and 25 professional Accountants drawn from the 25 Local Governments of Delta State, Nigeria. However, a final sample of 40 respondents was randomly selected for investigations. The pilot test conducted using 50 questionnaires with

Cronbach's Alpha statistical test of 0.783 was obtained (this exceeds the standard of 0.70). This was considered appropriate in achieving the research objectives. The collated data were analyzed using the Pearson Correlation model. The data collected were collated and analyzed with the aid of the SPSS data analysis tool.

5. Interpretation of Results

Table 1 Descriptive Statistic on Forensic Audit

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Forensic audit is capable of prosecuting the fraudsters, embezzlers and other financial criminals or suspects.	38	4.20	0.921
The forensic auditors, though not popular in Nigeria, are hired occasionally with the sole aim of unearthing fraudulent activities	38	4.06	1.063
Forensic audit can be used to trace, discover and recover laundered money and help in reducing cases of financial crimes bribery and money launderers	38	3.18	1.476
Valid N (listwise)	38		

Source: Field Survey, (2025).

From table 1, larger percentage of the respondents agreed that forensic audit is capable of prosecuting the fraudsters, embezzlers and other financial criminals or suspects and hence maintains a mean value of 4.20 with a standard deviation of 0.921. Furthermore, another set of correspondents also agreed that the forensic auditors, though not popular in Nigeria, are hired occasionally with the sole aim of unearthing fraudulent activities in Nigeria with a mean value of 4.06 and a standard deviation of 1.063. Finally, the last set of respondents agreed that forensic audit can be used to trace, discover and recover laundered money and help in reducing cases of financial crimes, bribery and money laundering and hence it maintain a mean value of 3.18 and standard deviation of 1.476.

The mean values of all the variables employed in the process of research were greater than 3. The required average of a five point Likert scale is 3. The researchers consequently upheld the prevalence of study variables.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistic on Litigation Support

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Litigation support is the process by which forensic accounting provide advice to attorneys on complex accounting matters that are relevant to a legal dispute	38	4.05	1.019
The calculation of the economic loss resulting from a breach of contract by the forensic accountant is necessary in the fight against financial crimes.	38	4.03	0.100
Litigation Support provides assistance of an accounting nature in a matter involving existing or pending litigation.	38	3.85	1.090
Valid N (listwise)	38		

Source: Field Survey, (2025).

From table 2, larger percentage of the respondents agreed that litigation support is the process by which forensic accounting provide advice to attorneys on complex accounting matters that are relevant to a legal dispute and hence maintain a mean value of 4.05 with a standard deviation of 1.019. Furthermore, another set of correspondents also agreed that the calculation of the economic loss resulting from a breach of contract by the forensic accountant is necessary in the fight against financial crimes with a mean value of 4.03 and a standard deviation of 1.100. Finally, the last set of respondents was undecided as to whether litigation Support provides assistance of an accounting nature in a

matter involving existing or pending litigation and hence it maintain a mean value of 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.090.

The mean values of all the variables employed in the process of research were greater than 3. The researchers consequently upheld the prevalence of study variables since the mean of the 5-Likert scale that shows that the respondents agree is 3.00.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistic on Money Laundering

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Money laundering remains a major and costly form of fraud for both businesses and the overall global economy	38	3.58	1.325
Fraudsters use money laundering tactics to run their schemes without leaving a paper trail	38	3.14	1.496
Money laundering processes are difficult to trace hence the forensic accounting expert is needed	38	3.67	1.260
Valid N (listwise)	38		

Source: Field Survey, (2025).

From table 3 , larger percentage of the respondents agreed that money laundering remains a major and costly form of fraud for both businesses and the overall global economy and hence maintain a mean value of 3.58 with a standard deviation of 1.325. Another set of correspondents also agreed that fraudsters use money laundering tactics to run their schemes without leaving a paper trail with a mean value of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 1.496. Finally, the last set of respondent also agreed that money laundering processes are difficult to trace hence the forensic accounting expert is needed with a mean value of 3.67 and standard deviation of 1.260.

The mean values of all the variables employed in the process of research were greater than 3. This implies that the respondents agreed to all the questions since it require an average of 3.00 on a five point Likert scale questionnaire. The researchers consequently upheld the prevalence of study variables.

Table 4 Descriptive Statistic on Bribery

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Litigation support is the process by which forensic accounting provide advice to attorneys on complex accounting matters that are relevant to a legal dispute.	38	3.55	1.336
The calculation of the economic loss resulting from a breach of contract by the forensic accountant is necessary in the fight against financial crimes.	38	3.53	1.395
Litigation Support provides assistance of an accounting nature in a matter involving existing or pending litigation.	38	3.27	1.400
Valid N (listwise)	38		

From table 4 above, a larger percentage of respondents agreed that forensic investigation in Nigeria can positively reduce the rate of bribery among public office holders in Nigeria and hence maintain a mean value of 3.55 with a standard deviation of 1.336. Another set of correspondents also agreed that Investigation skills of forensic accountant are relevant in the fighting bribery among public office holders in Nigeria with a mean value of 3.53 and a standard deviation of 1.395. However, the last set of respondent were undecided as to whether establishing forensic accounting

investigation unit can lead to the prevention of cases of bribery in the public service or not and hence it maintains a mean value of 3.27 and standard deviation of 1.400.

The mean values of all the variables employed in the process of research were greater than 3; this implies that the required average of a five point Likert scale is 3. The researchers consequently upheld the prevalence of study variables.

6. Test of Hypotheses

A total of four null hypothesized bivariate associations were postulated in the study. In an attempt to actualize the eclectic objective of the research work, the researcher employed correlation analysis as a tool in testing the hypotheses considering the fact that it gives a synchronized account of the relationship between the variables under investigation using SPSS.

6.1. Decision Rule

If the probability value (PV) in the coefficient table is less than 0.05 alpha level and positive, Reject the null hypotheses and accept significant relationship.

If the probability value (PV) is greater than 0.05 alpha level, Accept the null hypothesis and accept insignificant relationship.

6.1.1. *Ho₁Forensic audit has no significant effect on the reduction of money laundry in Nigeria.*

Table 5 Presentation of correlation analysis output for forensic audit and money laundry reduction

Correlations		Forensic Audit	Money Laundry
Forensic Audit	Pearson Correlation	1	0.865**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	38	38
Money Laundry	Pearson Correlation	0.865**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

The result of the correlation analysis in table 5 above indicates a correlation value of 0.865 which implies that about 86.50% variation in the dependent variable is caused by the variation of the independent variable. It means that when forensic audit is increased, there is going to be an increase in reduction in money laundry activities and vice versa. The correlation table shows that forensic audit maintains a probability value of 0.000 with a positive correlation. The implication is that forensic audit and reduction in money laundry have significant relationship. On this back drop, the analysis therefore reveals that forensic audit is capable of reducing money laundry.

Hence, this result accounts for the rejection of the null hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between forensic audit and money laundry reduction.

6.1.2. *Ho₂Forensic audit has no significant effect on reduction of bribery in Nigeria.*

The result of the correlation analysis in table 6 above shows a correlation value of 0.739 which implies that about 73.90% variation in the dependent variable is caused by the variation of the independent variable. It means that when forensic audit is increased, there is going to be an increase reduction in bribery activities and vice versa. The correlation table shows that forensic audit maintains a probability value of 0.042 with a positive correlation. The implication is that forensic audit and reduction in bribery has significant relationship. The analysis indicates that forensic audit is capable of reducing bribery. The researcher therefore, rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between forensic audit and bribery reduction.

Table 6 Presentation of correlation analysis output for forensic audit and reduction of bribery

Correlations			
		Forensic Audit	Bribery
Forensic Audit	Pearson Correlation	1	0.739**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.042
	N	38	38
Bribery	Pearson Correlation	0.739**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.042	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

6.1.3. *Ho3. Litigation support has no significant effect on reduction of money laundry in Nigeria.*

Table 7 Presentation of correlation analysis output for litigation support and reduction in money laundry

Correlations			
		Litigation Support	Money Laundry
Litigation Support	Pearson Correlation	1	0.839**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	38	38
Money Laundry	Pearson Correlation	0.839**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

The result of the correlation analysis in table 7 shows a correlation value of 0.839 which implies that about 83.90% variation in the dependent variable is caused by the variation of the independent variable. It means that when litigation support is increased, there is going to be an increase reduction in money laundry activities and when forensic audit decreases, the opposite holds. The correlation table shows that litigation support maintains a probability value of 0.000 with a positive correlation. The implication is that litigation support and reduction in money laundry have significant relationship. Thus, the analysis indicates that litigation support is capable of reducing money laundry. Hence, the rejection of the null the hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between litigation support and money laundry reduction.

6.1.4. *Ho4. Litigation support has no significant effect on reduction of bribery in Nigeria.*

Table 8 Presentation of correlation analysis output for litigation support and bribery

Correlations			
		Litigation Support	Bribery
Litigation Support	Pearson Correlation	1	0.625**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.049
	N	38	38
Bribery	Pearson Correlation	0.625**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.049	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

From the result of the correlation analysis in table 8 above, the correlation value is 0.625 which implies that about 62.50% variation in the dependent variable is caused by the variation of the independent variable. It means that when litigation support is increased, there is going to be an increase reduction in bribery activities and when it decreases, the opposite holds. The correlation table shows that litigation support maintains a probability value of 0.049 with a positive correlation. The implication is that forensic audit and reduction in bribery has significant relationship. The analysis therefore reveals that litigation support is capable of reducing bribery. The paper therefore rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between litigation support and reduction in bribery.

7. Discussion of Findings

The test of hypothesis one (H_{01}) showed a correlation and significant values of 0.865 and 0.000 respectively. The result means that forensic audit used as a dimension of forensic accounting has the ability to cause 86.5% change in money laundry (measure of financial crimes). This result indicates that 13.5% of the changes in money laundry cannot be traced to forensic audit but other factors not captured in this study. The correlation value is a positive value which means that they move towards the same direction, an increase in the independent variable will result to an increase in the dependent variable.

Furthermore, the value of 0.000 which represents the probability or the significance level indicates the presence of a relationship. This means that the independent variable (forensic audit) significantly affects the dependent variable (reduction in money laundry). This conclusion is because the significant value is less than 0.05. The study therefore rejected the null hypothesis of no significant effect and accepts the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between forensic audit and money laundry reduction.

The test of hypothesis two (H_{02}) showed a correlation and significant values of 0.739 and 0.042 respectively. The result means that forensic audit used as a dimension of forensic accounting has the ability to cause 73.9% change in bribery (measure of financial crimes). This result indicates that 26.1% of the changes in bribery cannot be traced to forensic audit but other factors not captured in this study. The correlation value is a positive value which means that they move towards the same direction an increase in the independent variable will result to an increase in the dependent variable. Thus, the value of 0.042 which represents the probability or the significance level indicates the presence of a relationship. This means that the independent variable (forensic audit) significantly affects the dependent variable (reduction in bribery). This conclusion is because the significant value is less than 0.05. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis of no significant effect and accepts the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between forensic audit and bribery reduction.

In a similar vein, the result of the correlation analysis in table 6 above shows a correlation value of 0.739 which implies that about 73.90% variation in the dependent variable is caused by the variation of the independent variable. It means that when forensic audit is increased, there is going to be an increase reduction in bribery activities and vice versa. The correlation table shows that forensic audit maintains a probability value of 0.042 with a positive correlation. The implication is that forensic audit and reduction in bribery has significant relationship. On the strength of this, the researchers conclude that forensic audit is capable of reducing bribery.

The test of hypothesis three (H_{03}) showed a correlation and significant values of 0.839 and 0.000 respectively. The result means that litigation support used as a dimension of forensic accounting has the ability a cause 83.9% change in money laundry (measure of financial crimes). This result indicates that 16.1% of the changes in money laundry cannot be traced to litigation support but other factors not captured in this study. The correlation value is a positive value which means that they move towards the same direction and an increase in the independent variable will result to an increase in the dependent variable. Similarly, the value of 0.000 which represents the probability or the significance level indicates the presence of a relationship. This means that the independent variable (litigation support) significantly affects the dependent variable (reduction in money laundry). This conclusion is because the significant value is less than 0.05. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis of no significant effect and accepts the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between litigation support and money laundry reduction.

The test of hypothesis four (H_{04}) showed a correlation and significant values of 0.625 and 0.049 respectively. The result means that litigation support used as a dimension of forensic accounting has the ability to cause 62.5% change in bribery (measure of financial crimes). This result indicates that 37.5% of the changes in bribery cannot be traced to litigation support but other factors not captured in this study. The correlation value is a positive value which means that they move towards the same direction and increase in the independent variable will result to an increase in the dependent variable. Thus, the value of 0.049 which represents the probability or the significance level indicates the presence of a relationship. This means that the independent variable (litigation support) significantly affects the dependent variable

(reduction in bribery). This conclusion is because the significant value is less than 0.05. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis of no significant effect and accepts the alternative hypothesis of significant relationship between litigation support and bribery reduction.

8. Conclusion

The empirical research was carried out to examine the effect of forensic accounting on financial crimes reduction in Nigeria. Four hypotheses were formulated and tested. The results from the four hypothesis tested indicates that the two dimensions of forensic accounting have a positive significant effect on the two measures of financial crimes reduction. Based on the results of the analyses, the study concludes that forensic accounting has significant effect on financial crimes reduction. More so, both variables move in the same direction as they correlate positively.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

- Forensic audit should be considered as a regular exercise whenever there is suspicion of money laundry
- Forensic audit department should be created in all anti-craft organizations to ensure proper investigation of financial crimes
- Forensic accounting experts should be involved in legal dispute and be allowed to provide evidence in the courtroom.
- The forensic accountant should be contacted for litigation services whenever there is a suspicious contract, to find out if bribe was given or taken.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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Appendix

8.1. Questionnaires

Tick the appropriate box

1. **Gender:** Male

Female

2. **Educational Qualification**

ACCA, ICAN/ANAN, others

MSc/MBA/MA and above

HND/BA/BEd/BSc

NCE/ND and Below

3. Years of Knowledge/Experience

- Above 20
- 11 – 20
- 10 and below

Questionnaire on Forensic Audit

	FORENSIC AUDIT	SA	A	U	D	SD
1	Forensic audit is capable of prosecuting the fraudsters, embezzlers and other financial criminals or suspects.					
2	The forensic auditors, though not popular in Nigeria, are hired occasionally with the sole aim of unearthing fraudulent activities					
3	Forensic audit can be used to trace, discover and recover laundered money and help in reducing cases of financial crimes bribery and money launderers					

Questionnaire on Litigation Support

	LITIGATION SUPPORT	SA	A	U	D	SD
4	Litigation support is the process by which forensic accounting provide advice to attorneys on complex accounting matters that are relevant to a legal dispute					
5	The calculation of the economic loss resulting from a breach of contract by the forensic accountant is necessary in the fight against financial crimes.					
6	Litigation Support provides assistance of an accounting nature in a matter involving existing or pending litigation.					

Questionnaire on Money Laundry

	MONEY LAUNDRY	SA	A	U	D	SD
7	Money laundering remains a major and costly form of fraud for both businesses and the overall global economy					
8	Fraudsters use money laundering tactics to run their schemes without leaving a paper trail					
9	Money laundering processes are difficult to trace hence the forensic accounting expert is needed					

Questionnaire on Bribery

	BRIBERY	SA	A	U	D	SD
10	Litigation support is the process by which forensic accounting provide advice to attorneys on complex accounting matters that are relevant to a legal dispute.					
11	The calculation of the economic loss resulting from a breach of contract by the forensic accountant is necessary in the fight against financial crimes.					
12	Litigation Support provides assistance of an accounting nature in a matter involving existing or pending litigation.					

Correlation Analysis

Presentation of correlation analysis output for forensic audit and money laundry reduction

Correlations			
		Forensic Audit	Money Laundry
Forensic Audit	Pearson Correlation	1	0.865**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	38	38
Money Laundry	Pearson Correlation	0.865**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

.Presentation of correlation analysis output for forensic audit and reduction of bribery

Correlations			
		Forensic Audit	Bribery
Forensic Audit	Pearson Correlation	1	0.739**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.042
	N	38	38
Bribery	Pearson Correlation	0.739**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.042	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Presentation of correlation analysis output for litigation support and reduction in money laundry

Correlations			
		Litigation Support	Money Laundry
Litigation Support	Pearson Correlation	1	0.839**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	38	38
Money Laundry	Pearson Correlation	0.839**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Presentation of correlation analysis output for litigation support and bribery

Correlations			
		Litigation Support	Bribery
Litigation Support	Pearson Correlation	1	0.625**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.049
	N	38	38
Bribery	Pearson Correlation	0.625**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.049	
	N	38	38

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)